
Evaluating Hybrid Convolutional Models for Accelerator-Based Neutrino Detectors

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Abstract

A computer vision study aims to exploit imaging systems generated from Monte Carlo simulations that model neutrino detection systems and their respective oscillation associations. The **Nova** experiment, used as a reference, captures muon and electron neutrino data. By providing a binary classification of these two flavor states, automatic detection using these models proposes potential approaches for the real detection of these particles. To this end, an architecture is proposed that integrates convolutional networks to extract feature maps, connecting them to a Random Forest, which infers the classification of these two flavor oscillations.

Introduction

Neutrinos are one of the smallest particles known and have a mass of practically zero, traveling at an ultra-relativistic speed, making it difficult to determine their precise mass. These particles can be referred to in 3 possible flavors, represented as $\alpha = \{e, \mu, \tau\}$, which represent the possible states of oscillation [3, 8, 9]. To detect these particles, experiments such as the **Nova** experiment consider two detectors: one established at Fermilab and another 810 km away, which uses the source of a beam of neutrinos that are directly observable and measure the transformation of muonic neutrinos to electron neutrinos.

The detection configuration of this neutrino beam comes from the generation of these particles. The figure shown demonstrates Fermilab's accelerator, in Figure 1, which provides a brief description of the particle accelerator responsible for inserting neutrinos into the detectors. This instrument makes it possible to produce two proton lines: a low-energy one at 8 GeV and a high-energy one at 120 GeV, which hit a target, producing secondary beams of pions, muons, kaons and neutrinos that are used in the experiments.

Figure 1. Fermilab particle accelerator. Example of the particle accelerator configuration responsible for injecting high-energy protons, which decay into neutrinos and provide the NuMI beamline for particle detectors. Credits: [20]

The injector captures the Booster's low-energy protons and accelerates them to high energy at 120 GeV, where these highly energetic charged particles hit a carbon sample to generate pions that decay into muons and muonic neutrinos, resulting in the NuMI beamline, which are used in the detectors of experiments such as **Nova**, used to identify neutrinos arriving at the [20] experiment. The NuMI Off-axis νe

appearance experiment was developed to study the oscillation of muonic to electron neutrinos. It consists of configuring two detectors to maximize the acquisition of data associated with the oscillation of electron neutrinos before reaching the far detector, which is 810 km away and where neutrinos travel through the Earth's crust, potentially generating elastic scattering with neutrons and electrons. The aforementioned interaction between the electron neutrinos led to the differentiation between the oscillation probabilities of a neutrino and antineutrino beam in the **Nova** experiment, making it possible to discriminate between the normal and inverted hierarchy of the masses [7].

The detector mentioned in the experiment consists of liquid scintillators that interact with the medium and the light source is collected by the electronic front section. The scintillators are carried by planes that make up separate extruded PVC cells. The Far Detector of the **Nova** describes the sum of 344,064 PVC cells arranged in planes of 384 cells. In the interaction of neutrinos that generate charged particles, the process ionizes the scintillators as they travel through them. The emitted light travels until it is reflected by the PVC walls of the cells, and the signal passes through the fiber until it reaches a photodiode.

Figure 2. Description of the Nova detector mechanism. The figure shows the hits produced by the passage of charged particles and the deposition of energy in the scintillator cells. Credits: [20]

When a particle ionizes the liquid scintillator, such as muons or electrons, the process excites the scintillator molecules which, in turn, emit light in the violet spectrum with a wavelength of 425 nm. The light travels to the fluorescent dye in the wavelength-shifting fiber, which will be partially trapped inside the fiber by total internal reflection. In the image described above Figure 2, the red dotted line represents the neutrino lines generated by Fermilab, showing the interactions at the interface and on the detector side. The collection of scintillation light at the end of the fiber is exposed to a pixel in an avalanche photodiode array that records the intensity and arrival time of the photon emission signals [20].

The detections used in this project come from simulated images with the aim of approximating the results of the **Nova** experiment. In the modeled data, the neutrino beams are traveling in the direction of the z-axis, and at each interaction the images consist of two planes called X-view and Y-view.

Figure 3. Description of the Nova detector mechanism. The figure shows the hits produced by the passage of charged particles and the deposition of energy in the scintillator cells

The goal is to develop a binary classifier using a Convolutional Neural Network associated with the Random Forest algorithm, in which the outputs refer to the identification of ν_μ and ν_e . The convolutional networks will be responsible for extracting features, which will serve as a database for input to the Random Forest. In Figure 3, the images describe the perception of charged current interactions of the muonic flavor of the neutrino, configuring a duplicate input in the two visualization perspectives of neutrino detection, which will be discussed in later topics.

Neutrino States and Oscillation

Neutrino oscillation theory describes three neutrino flavors, defined by their interaction with charged leptons at charged-current weak vertices: electron neutrinos (ν_e), muon neutrinos (ν_μ), and tau neutrinos (ν_τ). These flavors correspond to three mass states: ν_1 , ν_2 , and ν_3 , with respective masses m_1 , m_2 , and m_3 . When neutrino mixing occurs, the neutrino mass eigenstates are not aligned with the neutrino flavor states. This misalignment is described by the Pontecorvo-Maki-Nakagawa-Sakata (PMNS) matrix [17, 19], as shown in the following matrix equation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \nu_e \\ \nu_\mu \\ \nu_\tau \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} U_{e1} & U_{e2} & U_{e3} \\ U_{\mu1} & U_{\mu2} & U_{\mu3} \\ U_{\tau1} & U_{\tau2} & U_{\tau3} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \nu_1 \\ \nu_2 \\ \nu_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The PMNS matrix is analogous to the CKM matrix in that it transforms flavor eigenstates to mass eigenstates. Neutrino oscillations result from the mixing of these states, and experimentally, this can be observed as neutrinos change flavor as they travel away from the source.

When a neutrino is created, it is produced through the weak interaction in a specific flavor state, such as ν_α . This state parameter can vary among electron, muon, and tau neutrinos. The function below can improve the visualization of the neutrino decay mechanism.

$$|\psi(0, 0)\rangle = |\nu_\alpha\rangle = U_{\alpha1}|\nu_1\rangle + U_{\alpha2}|\nu_2\rangle + U_{\alpha3}|\nu_3\rangle \quad (2)$$

The coefficients described in Equation 2 refer to the elements of the PMNS matrix associated with the flavor states and mass states, which acquire phase terms ϕ as a function of the distance L traveled in the vacuum and the time elapsed.

$$|\psi(L, t)\rangle = U_{\alpha1}|\nu_1\rangle e^{-i\phi_1} + U_{\alpha2}|\nu_2\rangle e^{-i\phi_2} + U_{\alpha3}|\nu_3\rangle e^{-i\phi_3} \quad (3)$$

By evolving in a vacuum, Equation 3 demonstrates the acquisition of phases among the terms of the wave function, represented as $\phi_i = E_i t - |\mathbf{p}_i|L$, where E_i is associated with the energy and the second term with the momentum [11]. One of the main objectives of the experiment is primarily the observation of electron neutrinos. The equation below shows the probability of a muon neutrino oscillating to an electron neutrino. To simplify the calculation, it is customary to assume that the CP phase δ is null, considering only the Majorana phases, assuming that neutrinos are their own antiparticles.

$$P(\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e) = \sin^2(\theta_{23}) \sin^2(2\theta_{13}) \sin^2(\Delta m_{32}^2 \Phi) + \cos^2(\theta_{23}) \sin^2(2\theta_{13}) \sin^2(\Delta m_{21}^2 \Phi) + \cos(\theta_{13}) \sin(2\theta_{12}) \sin(2\theta_{13}) \sin(2\theta_{23}) \sin(\Delta m_{32}^2 \Phi) \sin(\Delta m_{21}^2 \Phi) \cos(\Delta m_{32}^2 \Phi) \quad (4)$$

The probability can be affected by four main factors: neutrino energy E , the size of the propagation path, mass splitting, and the mixing angle. The proportionality relationships indicate an increase in the neutrino oscillation rate as the mass difference increases and the energy decreases, making the process faster [22]. The probability described above pertains to neutrino oscillations in a vacuum, while neutrinos can also propagate through matter. As these particles travel through matter, electron neutrinos undergo coherent forward charged current scattering with electrons from matter. This so-called Mikheyev-Smirnov-Wolfenstein (MSW) effect [2, 18, 21] will be derived assuming only two flavors of neutrinos, electron and muonic, which serves as the basis for **No ν a**.

The relationship between the calculation of this probability and neutrino oscillations can be elucidated with an oscillogram, as shown in Figure 4. This figure illustrates the sensitivity of neutrino oscillation experiments with particle accelerators to different energies and trajectories.

Figure 4. Oscillogram of neutrino detectors. The figure shows a comparison of experiments with atmospheric neutrinos and those based on the generation of beams by particle accelerators. Credits: [4]

The oscillation of these particles produced by accelerators has become an important tool for analyzing these properties, generally involving a fixed baseline where the length of the neutrino's trajectory is determined by the energy spectrum available in the experiment. As shown in Figure 4, the oscillogram introduces this fixed baseline of the experiment, which is sensitive to oscillation probabilities at specific energies.

The aim of this investigation is to observe channels where the oscillation probability is suppressed or increased. If experiments could work with similar resonant energies and

within the baseline at a distance of thousands of kilometers, determining the oscillation probabilities of neutrinos would be relatively simple.

However, as can be seen from the oscillogram, the baseline of accelerator-based neutrino experiments is typically confined to relatively shallow trajectories, resulting in a rather poor oscillation pattern, which severely limits their capabilities and leads to various degeneracies [4].

Monte Carlo Simulation and Data Comparison

This section discusses an analytical approach to the events simulated using Monte Carlo models, which served as tabular input data for the convolutional filters. In the **Nova** experiment, neutrinos can be identified through the following interactions: charged current (ν_e CC), charged current muonic (ν_μ CC), and neutral current (NC), as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 5. Topology of interaction events. Respectively ν_μ CC, ν_e CC, and NC interactions. Credits: [22]

The electron neutrino signal comes from an electromagnetic shower corresponding to Charged Current ν_e interactions. The electron neutrino interacts with matter by exchanging a boson that creates an electron and a proton or another hadron, depending on how deeply the neutrino interacts with the nucleus. The electron initially loses energy in the form of Bremsstrahlung radiation [22]. The figure showing the different interactions of the neutrinos serves as the basis for the convolutional network model that extracts the feature map, thus configuring the input for the Random Forest.

The Monte Carlo model helps understand the systems that appear in the interacting particles of the **Nova** detectors. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to examine the performance of the simulation by comparing the model results with detection data from the experiment for further validation [22]. The first step is to analyze events by the number of hits, calorimetric energy, longest prong, and vertex z, which serve as the base system of study for the next detector, as shown in Figure 12 below.

(a) Calorimetric energy ratio: MC and original data

(b) Number of hits ratio: MC and original data

(c) Comparison of prong length: MC and original data

(d) Vertex z-coordinates: MC and original data

Figure 6. Near Detector Data. Comparison of Monte Carlo simulation distributions and data captured from the **No ν a** experiment. Credits: [22]

The figures above refer to the detection system close to the experiment. In Figure 12a, the calorimetric energy is configured to determine the energy of the neutrino that caused the event, allowing the reconstruction of the neutrino energy. As seen in the graphs from Figures 12a to 10d, the models from the Monte Carlo simulation and the captured data converge approximately, indicating stability and coherence in the simulation of events in the near detector through this simulation practice.

Figure 12 also shows good coherence between data and Monte Carlo simulations in the region from 20 to 200 hits and the calorimetric energy range from 1 to 3 GeV. The disparity above 3 GeV is attributed to the Birk effect, giving credibility to the Monte Carlo simulations relative to the data from the **No ν a** experiment [22].

Observations of the events in the simulation are also of high importance to the study. To ensure that the events are close to reality, it is necessary to check the error that may be associated with the coordinate relationship in which the events are acquired or simulated, as shown in Figure 7.

(a) Relation of events in x-coordinates: MC and original data

(b) Relation of events in y-coordinates: MC and original data

Figure 7. Comparison of Monte Carlo simulation distributions and data from the **No ν a** experiment. Credits: [22]

As shown in the two graphs above, in addition to the z-vertex coordinates shown in Figure 10d, the proximity of the values of these other two coordinates discretize simulation curves that support the argument that the Monte Carlo models used in the study are close to the reality of neutrino detection, which respectively serve as input for the classification model.

Random Forest with Convolutional Neural Networks

The objective of this work is associated with the classification of two interactions, a neutrino-muon interaction and a neutrino-electron interaction. The images generated from the Charged Current interactions are shown in Figure 8, with their original data representations of the interactions and the data from the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) sample that was inserted to solve a problem of balancing the dataset.

(a) Example of an original figure on muon-neutrino interaction.

(b) Example of a given SMOTE on muon-neutrino interaction.

(c) Example of an original data on electron-neutrino interaction.

(d) Example of a given SMOTE on electron-neutrino interaction.

Figure 8. Application of the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique. Comparative analysis between original samples for the test set and generated samples for training.

The data is subdivided into two main branches, where each input image X-View and Y-View provide a dual character to the signals that will be processed by the input convolutional filters, serving as extractors of feature maps. The data captured through Monte Carlo simulations totals four samples, each simulating 7,000 neutrino interaction events of various types but in different proportions. This implies that events are more common for CC ν_μ interactions than for CC ν_e interactions.

Figure 8 shows that the application of the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique helped balance the dataset. However, to ensure coherent use of this methodology, it was only applied at the training data stage. The model performed the extraction of features and the mapping of the generated and test datasets onto the real database to observe the performance of the Random Forest relative to the application set closest to reality. After applying the smoothing technique, the total number of X-View and Y-View labels among the four events reached 37,254 for both perspectives of the data augmentation process. The proposed model for mapping this set of images is a hybrid model. The first stage is responsible for extracting a map of features using convolution kernels. Finally, a Dense layer generates an input vector that is processed by the Random Forest algorithm, which serves as a binary classification system to infer the classes of muon or electron neutrinos, as shown in Figure 9, which describes the feature extractor.

Figure 9. Feature Extractor preview. Description of the mechanism for extracting the feature mapping and also for generating the classifier’s input vector.

The convolutional section is introduced using the TensorFlow package. The step preceding the Random Forest algorithm involves acquiring the mapping of the characteristics of the images used for training. This dataset serves as input for the algorithm to classify the interaction type of the simulation event, determining whether it corresponds to the arrival of a muon neutrino or the appearance of an electron neutrino.

Random Forest can solve overfitting problems and optimize diversity through the randomness of input variables and combined trees. The algorithm is not significantly affected by outliers [14]. The process known as bootstrap aggregation, or bagging, involves randomly extracting a portion of the training data for each Decision Tree [5], with the remaining data used for cross-validation in evaluating the classifier’s performance. This mechanism, described by the Random Forest algorithm, uses data from the vectors coming out of the final layer in Figure 9, which contains an activation function to configure the values in the input vector for the neutrino interaction classifier.

Convolutional Neural Network and Feature Extraction

The method proposed in this article combines Random Forest algorithms with a convolutional filter feature extraction system. Neutrino interaction images are transformed into vectors of real values that feed the Random Forest algorithm. The convolutional neural network acts as the feature generator for the binary classifier of neutrino interactions.

Figure 10. Comparative sample of two interaction events. Interactions between two types of neutrino flavors and their respective Dense layer output vectors.

Figure 10 provides a visualization of the output vectors used for the inference of the Random Forest algorithms. The feature extraction occurs in the convolutional layers and follows a pooling practice, resulting in a feature vector from a Dense layer. Convolutional networks are powerful computational tools widely used for recognition tasks, consisting of convolutional kernels and pooling layers that extract relevant features from input images.

These applications take advantage of the convolution mechanism, which combines two signals to form a third output signal. The mathematical definition of the convolution operation, used for feature extraction from input images, is shown in the equation below [12]:

$$(f * g)[n] = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} f[m]g[n - m] \quad (5)$$

Using Equation 5, the convolution procedure is carried out by functions f and g in n positional iterations or depending on the time index of the output signal. For feature extraction from input images, this refers to the dot product at each position, producing the feature mapping at the output of the convolution filters [12]. Figures 10.b and 10.d illustrate the steps that use these feature maps to place the resulting mapping from the model into a low-dimensional space, specifically a vector of 200 units, which enters the Random Forest algorithm to discriminate neutrino interactions.

Note that the output values of the Dense layer vary between -0.5 and 0.5 due to the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function. ReLU is widely adopted in deep learning studies for its ability to introduce sparsity and alleviate the vanishing gradient problem [13].

Before testing the hybrid convolutional network models, we will discuss the application of neural networks as classifiers. The specific features of the model architecture are listed in Table 1.

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Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
x_projection (InputLayer)	(None, 100, 80, 1)	0
y_projection (InputLayer)	(None, 100, 80, 1)	0
conv2d	(None, 100, 80, 32)	160
conv2d_2	(None, 100, 80, 32)	160
conv2d_1	(None, 99, 79, 32)	4128
conv2d_3	(None, 99, 79, 32)	4128
concatenate	(None, 198, 79, 32)	0
conv2d_4	(None, 197, 78, 32)	4128
flatten	(None, 491712)	0
dense_1	(None, 1)	491713

Table 1. Summary of the CNN model layers and parameters

The hyperparameters were set with a learning rate of 0.005 and trained for 10 epochs, with 400 steps per epoch and a batch size of 20. The dataset consisted of four simulations, each containing seven thousand neutrino interaction events. Half of these events were used for training with balanced data, while the other half were used for testing without applying the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique. The subsequent iterations showed a respective profile of the decrease in the cost function, binary cross-entropy, and the process of inferring the mapping for the validation and training sections, as shown in Figure 11.

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(a) Decline of the binary cross-entropy function in validation and training.

(b) Accuracy comparison between training and validation processes.

Figure 11. Evaluation of training and validation. Both charts above describe how the convolutional neural network model learns from the neutrino dataset.

The accuracy acquired from the evaluation metrics of the convolutional network model as classifiers reached values close to 37%, indicating less than desirable performance in the context of classification. However, it showed high accuracy, as can be seen from the curves discussed in Figure 11.b. Additionally, the minimization of the cost function using the Adam optimizer from TensorFlow demonstrated consistent validation and training loss decay over the 10 epochs defined for the model. This effect of low precision with relatively high accuracy will not be observed in the following sections. Instead of using convolutional neural networks to discriminate neutrino interactions, they will be used as feature extractors, and the mapping will be input into a classifier. The next section will discuss two analyzed methods for this classification task.

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Random Forest or Extreme Gradient Boosting

The Random Forest algorithm was chosen for the model, but a second test using eXtreme Gradient Boosting, or XGBoost, was provided here as a comparison and to add other possible algorithm options for the inference system obtained at the output of the Dense layer. The Random Forest technique combines multiple decision trees to optimize the accuracy and robustness of each classification [15], while XGBoost will be highly efficient and scalable for implementing gradient boosting, which combines multiple models to create a more robust estimator [6, 23].

The intention is to demonstrate the introduction of two types of algorithms capable of dealing with complex data, but with different approaches, such as the bagging technique for Random Forest and boosting for the XGBoost option [10, 16]. Two approaches obtained similar accuracy and precision scores, the boosting technique containing 99.4% accuracy and precision at 66% , for the Random Forest, with no subtle improvement in their respective metrics, 99.4% for accuracy and precision of approximately 66%. The reference contact of the high accuracy and precision metrics is due to the high degree of complexity of the classification techniques mentioned and also to the balancing of the data. In the initial description of the model's input dataset, it was observed that there was a disparity between the interaction categories of the neutrinos, making the classification task unbalanced.

To overcome this problem, the SMOTE balancing technique was applied to the system. To obtain better classification results, 50% of the samples of neutrino interactions used to train the model were generated by balancing the labels. The test values represent half of the unbalanced dataset to acquire metrics and classifications with real values, in the Figure 12 below shows a confusion matrix that infers the number of classifications coherent with the respective labels.

(a) Confusion matrix with Random Forest

(b) Confusion matrix with Extreme Gradient Boosting.

Figure 12. Comparative analysis of the two classifiers. Process to verify the classification successes and errors of the proposed models.

The obvious finding presented above supports the argument that both approaches were successful in the classification process, with no differences justifying the proximity in the mentioned accuracy and precision values. The disproportionate nature of the test data, as shown in both matrices, is due to its imbalance, which refers to data coming directly from the real dataset.

Discussion and Future Work

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The study of the mechanism of neutrino oscillation has become a crucial area of particle physics, providing insights into the nature of neutrino interactions and being essential for understanding their properties and their implications for Standard Model physics. Neutrinos are among the most elusive particles discovered in nature; they are categorized as half spin fermions, contain no electric charge, and interact weakly with matter, making their identification extremely challenging [24].

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As these particles are complex to identify, computational mechanisms could automate the process of exploring data from accelerator-based neutrino detectors, especially from sensors that use scintillators to detect neutrino oscillation phenomena. The data on electron and muon neutrino flavors were used as classification labels for this study. However, other approaches can be provided in the utilization of hybrid convolutional models, such as dependency on metadata in classification based on types of detected interactions and other characteristics associated with these particles.

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Through convolutions to extract important features from the dataset, the hybrid models, combined with bagging methods such as Random Forest and boosting with XGBoost, efficiently performed the task of binary classification of the two neutrino flavors mentioned in the paper. Starting from the training base balanced through SMOTE, the test set received real values that verify how the model acts on non-generated values. The unbalanced values refer to the classification of only two flavors; future work could incorporate data and studies containing tau neutrinos to extend this context to multi-label classification.

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The hybrid models proved to be an important computational tool, as their purpose is to serve in the automatic identification of neutrinos from these detectors. An approach for future studies would be to populate the training database with different types of detectors, bringing diversity to the set and developing a more generalist approach to the task of classifying these neutrinos.

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Deep learning models have been extensively explored in particle physics for the reconstruction and classification of events detected through astrophysical experiments, such as IceCube [1]. These applications extend beyond accelerator-based experiments. Deep learning models not only discriminate the types of neutrinos detected but also assist in the reconstruction of these events, which can aid in the study of these particles.

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